

A0807

Experimental analysis of a pressurized 30 kW SOFC system with fuel gas recirculation at reaction temperature

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Abstract

Solid oxide cells (SOCs) are flexible and efficient energy conversion devices. Due to their multiple usage possibilities, like electricity generation and syngas production, they can support the global energy transition. However, to play a significant role in the future energy system SOC reactors have to reach the megawatt and multi-megawatt range.

To address process system issues expected in the higher power range, a 30 kW solid oxide fuel cell (SOFC) system with multiple reactors was set up at the German Aerospace Center in Stuttgart, Germany. This system can be operated under pressure and is equipped with a recirculation blower that recirculates the fuel electrode off-gas at reaction temperature. The system can be used to investigate the behavior of multi-reactor modules in a process system. Multi-reactors are necessary for scaling to higher power ranges and behave differently compared to single reactors. Furthermore, the test rig is capable of emulating gas turbine (GT) components to investigate the operation of a SOFC reactor in a GT/SOFC hybrid power plant.

This work will present experimental results to help clarify the above mentioned multi-reactor issues. The focus will be on the heat losses and unequal flow distribution inside the reactor, which result in different temperature and reactant conversion rates for the single reactors. Various methods, like fuel and pressure variation, are used to characterize these effects. It will be shown how these effects limit the operability of the system and affect the design and operation of process systems. Furthermore, it will be analyzed how process systems should be designed and operated to overcome these problems. Control approaches that improve operability are elaborated and their impact is discussed. Assuming that similar multi-reactor modules will constitute the building blocks of future multi-megawatt systems, generic operation strategies that are derived from the extensive experiments are presented.

Introduction

The growing global demand for energy from renewable sources is leading to new challenges for energy systems. Energy converters need to be developed to meet these challenges. On the one hand, the generation of electrical energy must be efficient and flexible. On the other hand, it is also necessary to develop solutions for hydrogen and syngas gas production from renewables in order to decarbonize industry and transport.

Electrochemical reactors with solid oxide cells can provide a solution due to their flexibility. First, these reactors can provide electrical energy efficiently and are both load and fuel flexible. Second, hydrogen and syngas can be produced in electrolysis mode (SOEC). Third, this flexibility can also be used to provide grid services and for energy storage in reversible mode (rSOC). With these features, SOC reactors can represent an important component for the energy transition. However, the power of commercially available modules is still too low. In order to have a significant impact on the future energy system, large modular SOC reactor modules with multi-megawatt output must be implemented [1, 2]. Up to now, academia has focused primarily on material development and the investigation of cells and their components. In order to address the fundamentals of modular multi-reactors the Institute of Engineering Thermodynamics of the German Aerospace Center in Stuttgart set up a test rig [3, 4] to investigate a 30 kW SOFC reactor module with 48 stacks under pressurized conditions including fuel off-gas recirculation at SOC reaction temperature.

The experimental results show that heat losses and flow distribution have a significant impact on the system's performance. This results in temperature profiles across the reactor and locally varying reactant utilizations. This work presents the test rig used and gives an overview of the experimental results.

1. Scientific Approach and Experimental Set-Up

Large SOC reactors are needed to increase the impact of SOC technology on the energy system. To investigate these in a system environment the DLR set up a test rig in Stuttgart that is presented in figure 1. The test rig is designed in such a way that various aspects can be investigated. It contains a recirculation device, which recirculates the fuel off-gases at reaction temperature. A reformer allows the usage of natural gas or simulated biogas (natural gas & carbon dioxide) as fuel. Furthermore, the SOFC reactor, the recirculation device and the reformer are located inside a pressure vessel for pressurized operation. The test rig is designed that it can emulate the interactions with a gas turbine (GT) to investigate SOFC/GT hybrid power plants.

Figure 1: The pressurized 30 kW SOFC system with fuel gas recirculation at reaction temperature. It contains the shown 30 kW SOFC reactor.

The SOFC reactor module consists of 1440 electrolyte supported cells grouped in six sub-reactors with six 30 cells stacks. Each sub-reactor is equipped with a separate power electronics channel to control their electrical currents. A sensor compartment at the bottom of the reactor module contains the sensor and power cables.

Figure 2 shows a simplified process flow diagram of the test rig. The incoming pressurized air is controlled by three separate mass flow controllers. First, an air flow is led through the sensor compartment for cooling. The pressure inside this compartment is controlled by a valve. The pressure vessel is purged and pressurized by the second air flow. The inlet temperature can be controlled by an electrical heater. The third air flow is preheated via a heat exchanger by a natural gas burner and led to the oxide side of the SOFC reactor. The incoming fuel is led through a desulfurizer. Subsequently it is mixed with the recirculated fuel off-gases and enters the reformer. Both air and fuel gas flow are cooled outside the vessel and then merged to minimize the pressure difference between air and fuel gas electrodes. A valve controls the system pressure. Afterwards, the remaining combustible molecules are oxidized and cooled.

Figure 2: Process flow diagram of the test rig [4] showing the main components and fluid flows.

With this set-up the temperature and voltage distribution inside the SOFC reactor is analyzed. Furthermore, the impact of the recirculation on the reactor as well as system performance is investigated. By varying the pressure the effect of pressurization on the electrochemistry, the overall system and the controllers is examined.

2. Experimental Results

The aim of the experimental investigations was to characterize the operating behavior of the SOFC reactor module through the variation of temperature, pressure, electrical power, fuel gas, its utilization and the recirculation rate. A control concept was developed to achieve this [3, 4]. In addition to the basic controllers, such as power and temperature controllers, also controllers were developed, which were necessary due to the specific layout of the system.

An example is the differential pressure controller for the pressure in the sensor compartment. Since the cooling flow of the sensor area is leaving through another

chimney, a second pressure control valve is necessary (cf. Figure 2). Pressure differences between sensor compartment and reactor volume are potentially damaging the reactor. Therefore, the controller must be robust and fast. This was achieved by means of a feed-forward controller that considers the characteristic of the valve as well as the flow entering the valve. A PI-controller only corrects the error of the feed-forward approach. The analysis in Figure 3 shows that the pressure difference is sufficiently small. Normally it is 1 mbar around the set point of 1 mbar (respectively 2 mbar for a short period).

Figure 3: Accuracy of the difference pressure controller over a period of more than 1000 h. The set value changes from 1 to 2 mbar for a short period.

An important aspect of the studies is the analysis of the temperature distribution within the reactor module. Figure 4 shows such a temperature distribution. Each temperature measurement represents a 30 cell stack. The top stacks have the highest temperatures and the bottom stacks are the coldest. The maximum difference can be up to 50 K. One reason for this is that the fuel gas flow is supplied from the bottom of each tower and has a high heat capacity due to the recirculation. The large temperature differences in combination with the flow distribution inside the reactor leads to different flow operating points for the cells inside the reactor. Furthermore, a broad variation of the operating temperature is not possible in a multi-reactor as the lowest and the highest temperature are near the limits of the design range of the cells.

Figure 4: Distribution of air outlet temperatures of the stacks during a stationary operating point. The hatched white-black pattern indicates thermocouples out of operation [7].

The fuel gas utilization was usually set between 70 and 90 %. The recirculation rate is determined by the thermal energy required for fuel gas preheating and steam methane

reforming. A fuel gas variation was performed. In addition to operation with hydrogen, natural gas and biogas (simulated by natural gas and carbon dioxide) were also used as these are attractive SOFC fuels. Unfortunately the pure operation with 100% natural gas was not possible in this arrangement. The temperature at the inlet of the reactor module was too low due to heat losses and the reforming reaction. Therefore hydrogen was added to the natural gas. Figure 4 shows impact of the CO₂ content in biogas on the SOFC reactor module's efficiency. As expected the efficiency drops with a higher share of CO₂.

Figure 5: Impact of the CO₂ content in the simulated biogas on the efficiency of the SOFC reactor module.

Due to the temperature distribution shown in Figure 4 the operation of such reactors is challenging. Therefore, a transient simulation model for large SOC reactors is under development [7] based on [8]. Figure 6 shows the simulation results for a similar reactor module. Each sub-reactor is constituted as an 1D+1D model. Each cell is discretized in flow direction and these cells are stacked. Besides fuel cell operation, the model will also be able to simulate water, co- and CO₂ electrolysis.

Figure 6: Simulation result of a similar SOC reactor module.

With this model it will be possible to increase the understanding of the behavior of large SOC reactor modules. Furthermore the simulations can be used to improve the operation strategies and develop control strategies and approaches.

3. Conclusions

The DLR's Institute of Engineering Thermodynamics is working on SOFC systems. A pressurized 30 kW SOFC system was built and operated to investigate SOFC reactors and their behavior in process systems. The system features fuel off-gas recirculation, is fuel flexible and can replicate gas turbine components to study the behavior of a SOFC in a SOFC/GT hybrid.

The experimental results show that heat losses and pressure losses lead to a temperature, reactant utilization and voltage distribution across the reactor module. For example, the difference between the stack with the highest and the stack with the lowest temperature can be up to 50 K. Due to these distributions, each stack operates at a different operating point. These effects can limit the operating range and cause the reactor to degrade faster.

To further investigate these effects, a transient 1D+1D simulation model is being developed, which can also be used to develop efficient and robust operation and control strategies.

Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 641073 (www.bio-hypp.eu). This work was financially supported by the project "SynLink – Energy: Synthetic e Fuels as key enabler for Sector Linking" of the Federal Ministry of Economic Affairs and Energy (BMWi, funding code 03EIV031C). The responsibility for the contents lies with the authors. Furthermore, the support from the German Federal Ministry of Economic Affairs and Energy for the project "DemoHydra" is gratefully acknowledged (support code: 03ET6032).

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Keywords: EFCF2020, SOx

Session A08: System design & performance

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